

Perceived Effectiveness of English Learning with AI and Its Linguistic Literacy

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Article information

Submission	24/12/2025	Revision received	30/03/2026
Acceptance	11/03/2026	Publication date	19/04/2026

Keywords:

Self-regulation
Artificial intelligence (AI)
AI-supported language learning
Perceived effectiveness
Linguistic literacy

Abstract: This study aims to develop a scale to measure individuals' perceptions of artificial intelligence (AI)-supported language learning tools validly and reliably and to examine the relationship between these perceptions and various individual variables. PEAI-LLS (perceived effectiveness of AI-based language learning scale) was developed, consisting of 14 items and two sub-dimensions: perceived learning and perceived facilitation. A total of 1018 university students at a university in the Aegean region participated in the study. Quantitative data were collected through online surveys. Based on the exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, the scale demonstrated a strong psychometric structure. Correlation and hierarchical regression analyses revealed that students' prior AI experience, general self-efficacy, and online self-regulation strategies significantly predicted PEAI-LLS scores. In particular, skills such as goal setting, task strategies, and environmental structuring have a strong effect on the perceived learning dimension. In addition, it was observed that individuals' trust in AI systems and their perceived benefits shape their attitudes towards the effectiveness of these technologies. Research findings reveal that the pedagogical success of AI-based language learning tools depends not only on technological infrastructure but also on their adaptability to learners' cognitive and psychological characteristics.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Öz-düzenleme
Yapay zekâ (YZ)
Yapay zekâ destekli dil öğrenimi
Algılanan etkililik
Dilsel okuryazarlık

Yapay Zekâ ile İngilizce Öğreniminin Algılanan Etkililiği ve Dilsel Okuryazarlık

Özet: Bu araştırmanın temel amacı, bireylerin yapay zekâ destekli dil öğrenme araçlarına yönelik algılarını geçerli ve güvenilir bir şekilde ölçmeye olanak tanıyan bir ölçek geliştirmek ve bu algının çeşitli bireysel değişkenlerle ilişkisini incelemektir. Bu doğrultuda geliştirilen Algılanan Yapay Zekâ Tabanlı Dil Öğrenme Etkinliği Ölçeği, algılanan öğrenme ve kolaylaştırma algısı olmak üzere iki alt boyuttan oluşan 14 maddelik bir yapı sunmaktadır. Araştırma, Ege Bölgesi'ndeki bir üniversitede öğrenim gören toplam 1018 üniversite öğrencisinin katılımıyla gerçekleştirilmiş; veriler nicel araştırma yöntemleri çerçevesinde çevrimiçi anketler yoluyla toplanmıştır. Açımlayıcı ve doğrulayıcı faktör analizleri sonucunda, ölçeğin güçlü bir psikometrik yapıya sahip olduğu belirlenmiştir. Korelasyon ve hiyerarşik regresyon analizleri, öğrencilerin önceki yapay zekâ deneyimlerinin, genel öz-yeterlik düzeylerinin ve çevrimiçi öz-düzenleme stratejilerinin PEAI-LLS puanlarını anlamlı şekilde yordadığını ortaya koymuştur. Özellikle hedef belirleme, görev stratejileri ve çevresel yapılandırma gibi beceriler algılanan öğrenme boyutu üzerinde güçlü bir etkiye sahiptir. Ayrıca, bireylerin yapay zekâ sistemlerine olan güveninin ve algıladıkları faydaların bu teknolojilerin etkililiğine yönelik tutumlarını şekillendirdiği gözlemlenmiştir. Araştırma bulguları, yapay zekâ tabanlı dil öğrenme araçlarının pedagojik başarısının yalnızca teknolojik altyapıya değil, aynı zamanda öğrencilerin bilişsel ve psikolojik özelliklerine uyarlanabilirliğine de bağlı olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır.

To Cite This Article: Aydoğan, H., Şanlı, Ö., Zanjani, S., & Akkuş, İ. (2026). Perceived effectiveness of English learning with AI and its linguistic literacy. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 20(1), 33–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19449952>

1. Introduction

Today, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are emerging as a fundamental driving force in the digital transformation of education systems. Especially in foreign language teaching, it has become possible to create more flexible, individualized, and interactive learning experiences by going beyond traditional classroom methods. AI-supported systems offer content tailored to the developmental levels of language learners, provide instant feedback, and transform the learning process into an individualized structure (Chen *et al.*, 2020). The main advantages of such systems include automatic assessment, content adaptation based on learner behavior, and natural language processing mechanisms supported by voice/verbal interactions. These systems, which allow students to progress at their own pace, also increase motivation to learn through gamification and visual supports. Compared to traditional teaching methods, AI-based language learning tools are seen as sustaining learners' interest longer and creating lasting learning outcomes.

However, the extent to which these technologies are effective in educational environments largely depends on the user's perceptions of these systems. Educational technologies should be evaluated not only for their technical success but also for their pedagogical acceptance and impact on learner attitudes. The technology acceptance model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), highlights perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as the main determinants of an individual's intention to use technology. In line with this model, scientifically measuring students' perceptions of artificial intelligence-supported language learning systems is a critical requirement for evaluating the systems' effectiveness and understanding learning outcomes. In this context, the Perceived Effectiveness of AI-based Language Learning Scale (PEAI-LLS) was developed to measure individuals' perceptions of AI-supported language learning experiences. The scale is structured into two dimensions: "perceived learning" and "perception of facilitation." The first dimension includes individuals' evaluations of the academic and cognitive contributions they obtain through these technologies. In contrast, the second dimension covers technical and pedagogical perceptions of the system's capacity to facilitate learning. In this respect, PEA-LLS is not only an evaluation tool but also provides a theoretical framework for analyzing the pedagogical value of technological learning environments.

1.1. Research Hypotheses

This study investigates the factors influencing learners' perceptions of the effectiveness of AI-supported language learning tools, focusing on the hypothesis given below:

- H1.* Participants' previous use of AI-based learning tools significantly increases PEA-LLS total scores.
- H2.* Participants' general self-efficacy levels positively predict PEA-LLS total scores.
- H3:* Students with high self-efficacy levels have higher scores on the perceived learning dimension.
- H4.* Online self-regulation skills (especially goal setting and task strategies) significantly predict PEA-LLS scores on the perceived learning sub-dimension.
- H5.* Students who find AI useful in education receive higher scores on the PEA-LLS scale.
- H6.* As trust in AI-based tools increases, students' perceived learning scores rise.

1.2. Conceptual Framework

1.2.1. *The place of artificial intelligence-supported learning tools in education*

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in education is reshaping not only teaching methods but also the design of learning environments and the roles of teachers and

students. AI-based learning systems offer a structure that can analyze individual learners' needs, adapt learning processes, and provide real-time feedback (Holmes et al., 2019). These systems provide an effective learning experience, especially in areas that require constant reinforcement and feedback, such as language learning. AI-powered language learning tools combine technologies such as automatic speech recognition (ASR), natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, and data mining to help learners improve their language skills across various aspects. These tools offer features such as pronunciation practice, personalized reading recommendations, auto-correction mechanisms, and content recommendations, making the learning process both interactive and learner-centered (Chen et al., 2020; Çakmak, 2022; Yıldız, 2024; Zhang, 2025). Research has shown that AI-supported learning systems have significant potential to increase students' motivation to learn. Features such as providing individualized feedback, creating personalized learning paths, and adapting content to students' development encourage active participation in the learning process (Arıkan & Zorba, 2019; Holmes et al., 2019). This helps students become individuals who plan and manage their own learning rather than merely passive recipients of information. In this context, learners' self-regulation skills—such as goal setting, strategy development, and time management—become more effective when supported by AI tools. Therefore, it is predicted that online self-regulation skills may be positively associated with the sub-dimensions of the PEAI-LLS scale (H4).

In addition, students' prior experience with AI-supported tools and their perceived trust in these technologies play an important role in their evaluations of the systems' effectiveness. It has been determined that individuals who find AI useful in education and trust these systems have more positive perceptions of the contributions of these tools to language learning (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). This strengthens the theoretical basis of hypotheses H5 and H6. The success of AI technologies is determined not only by the system's technical adequacy but also by an individual's perception of the system's self-efficacy. According to Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory, an individual's confidence in their own abilities increases their motivation to learn and the frequency with which they use strategies. Individuals with high self-efficacy adopt complex technological tools more easily and benefit more from these systems (H3). In light of this data, AI-supported learning tools are not only a technical innovation but also a pedagogical transformation tool. These tools pave the way for qualitative developments in education by providing a structure that accounts for individual differences, is grounded in data-driven decision-making, and enables systematic monitoring of learning outcomes.

1.2.2. Perceived effectiveness and technology acceptance

One of the most important factors in the effective use of technology in education is its perceived effectiveness. The concept of "perceived effectiveness" refers to an individual's subjective evaluation of a technology's contribution to learning outcomes (Teo, 2011). In this context, how effective a student finds an AI-supported learning tool depends on how useful and functional it is perceived to be, rather than on its overall success. The TAM, developed by Davis (1989), explains technology adoption in terms of two basic variables: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. According to this model, if an individual believes that using a system will benefit him/her and that it is easy to use, he/she will be more likely to adopt the technology and use it effectively. This model is widely used in the educational technology literature and helps individuals understand their attitudes, intentions, and behaviors towards technology (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). The perceived effectiveness of AI-based learning tools is an important variable that particularly affects learners' active participation in the learning process, their self-regulation strategies, and their motivation to

learn. Individuals' positive perceptions of these tools are directly related to the feedback mechanisms, personalization capabilities, and technical functionality they offer. Students evaluate a technology as effective not only because it is innovative, but also to the extent that it makes a real contribution to the learning process (Şumak *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, dimensions such as "perceived learning" and "perception of facilitation" of structures, as measured by the PEAI-LLS scale, directly overlap with the two basic structures predicted by TAM. The items on the scale subjectively reflect the extent to which individuals find AI-supported language learning tools useful and how easy they are to use. Thus, a potential bridge is established between learner attitudes, technological competence, and educational success. Accordingly, significant positive relationships are expected between individuals' perceptions of technological tools and their beliefs about the benefits they derive from these tools.

1.2.3. *Online self-regulation strategies*

Being successful in online learning environments is directly related to students' ability not only to access information but also to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning processes. In this context, self-regulation means that the learner directs his/her own learning process cognitively, motivationally, and behaviorally (Zimmerman, 2002). Self-regulation plays a critical role, especially in online learning environments that are more independent in terms of time and space. Online self-regulation strategies include setting learning goals, structuring the learning environment, time management, seeking help, using task strategies, and self-evaluation (Barnard *et al.*, 2009). These strategies allow the student to manage the process not only with external guidance but also with his/her own internal awareness. In this way, the learner can produce more flexible, effective, and sustainable solutions to the difficulties he/she encounters.

The ability of individuals to sustain academic success in online learning environments is closely related not only to access to content but also to their capacity to manage their learning. In this context, self-regulation skills are critical to an individual's ability to set their own learning goals, monitor and evaluate their learning process, and apply learning strategies effectively. The online self-regulated learning questionnaire (OSLQ), developed by Barnard and colleagues (2009), is widely used in the literature as a comprehensive instrument for assessing these skills in online learning environments. The OSLQ is structured into six basic dimensions to assess the extent to which individuals apply self-regulation strategies in online learning. The first of these dimensions, goal setting, refers to the student's ability to set clear, achievable, and measurable goals for the learning process. The second dimension, the environmental structuring, refers to the student's ability to organize a conducive learning environment. The third dimension, time management, covers the student's ability to organize learning activities according to a specific time plan.

The fourth strategy, help-seeking, involves the individual's tendency to seek support from teachers, friends, or other sources when necessary. This skill strengthens the social learning component by reducing the feeling of isolation in the online environment. The fifth dimension, task strategies, reveals the extent to which the student uses cognitive methods such as repeating information, taking notes, and summarizing to facilitate learning. Finally, self-evaluation is an individual's ability to critically assess their performance at the end of the learning process and make necessary adjustments. These six dimensions not only enhance the online learning experience but also increase an individual's adaptation to technology-supported learning environments. In this context, OSLQ is evaluated as a functional reference framework for

understanding the psychological and behavioral background of artificial intelligence-based language-learning scales such as the PEAI-LLS. The high use of these strategies is associated with greater academic success and more positive attitudes toward online learning (Kizilcec *et al.*, 2017). In addition, it is well established that an individual's self-regulation skills increase the perceived benefit of the tools offered in technological learning environments. In this context, it is predicted that significant positive relationships will be observed between the PEAI-LLS sub-dimensions and online self-regulation strategies (e.g., H4).

1.2.4. The role of self-efficacy and cognitive confidence

The learner's perception of control over their own learning process is central to contemporary learning approaches. Self-efficacy, one of the main determinants of this perception of control, is defined as an individual's belief in their capacity to complete a given task (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy directly affects not only the individual's motivation but also the use of cognitive strategies, level of effort, and commitment to the learning process. Therefore, individuals with high levels of self-efficacy tend to be more resilient, determined, and strategic in complex or innovative learning environments. The concept of self-efficacy has become even more important, especially in technology-supported learning contexts. The level of competence individuals feel when encountering a new digital system significantly determines whether they accept and use it (Compeau & Higgins, 1995). In environments that expect active participation and strategic thinking from users, such as artificial intelligence-based learning systems, self-efficacy is among the strongest predictors of technological acceptance. Research shows that individuals with high levels of self-efficacy in digital learning environments use learning materials more effectively and develop more positive attitudes toward learning (Tsai *et al.*, 2011). Another conceptual construct related to self-efficacy is cognitive confidence, the individual's belief in his/her cognitive processes. When evaluated in the context of PEAI-LLS, students with high self-efficacy and cognitive confidence are expected to score higher on the "perceived learning" dimension of AI-based language learning tools (see H2 and H3). When evaluated from this perspective, psychological structures such as self-efficacy and cognitive confidence in understanding perceptions of learning technologies are the main factors that affect not only individual success but also the system's overall acceptability.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This research was conducted to develop a valid and reliable scale to measure individuals' perceptions of artificial intelligence-supported language learning tools and to analyze these perceptions in relation to various psychological and demographic variables. The research was structured within the scope of both scale development and relational screening models. Quantitative methods were used in data collection and analysis.

2.2. Participants

A total of 414 university students at an Aegean region university participated in the first phase of the study during the fall semester of the 2023–2024 academic year. 59.2% of the participants were female, and 40.8% were male. 41.1% of the participants lived in dormitories, 36.2% in rented houses, and 22.7% with their families. In addition, 88.4% of participants reported using AI-based applications at least once. The average family income was \$766, with a range of \$400 to \$3,200. A total of 604 students participated in the second implementation phase. 59.8% of the participants were female, and 40.2% were male.

According to residence information, 40.2% of the participants lived in dormitories, 36.9% at homes, and 22.8% with their families. 88.2% of participants reported having previously used artificial intelligence tools. In this group, the average family income was 76,947 rubles, with a distribution ranging from 625 rubles to 3750 rubles.

Table 1.

Comparison of Demographic Characteristics of Participants (First and Second Data Collection Stages)

Variable	Category	Stage 1 (n = 414)		Stage 2 (n = 604)	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	245	59.2%	361	59.8%
	Male	169	40.8%	243	40.2%
Residence	Dormitory	170	41.1%	243	40.2%
	House	150	36.2%	223	36.9%
	With Family	94	22.7%	138	22.8%
AI use	Yes	366	88.4%	533	88.2%
	No	48	11.6%	71	11.8%
Family Income (₺)	Mean	\$ 1920		\$ 1923	
	Median	\$ 1925		\$ 1925	
	Std. Dev.	\$ 578		\$ 581.7	
	Min.–Max.	\$ 725 – \$ 3225		\$ 625- 3750	

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

The 14-item scale was developed to measure individuals' perceptions of artificial intelligence-based language learning tools. The scale includes two sub-dimensions: perceived learning and perceived facilitation. The OSLQ, developed by Barnard et al. (2009), is used to assess students' self-regulation skills in online learning. The 24-item scale measures six dimensions and is evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale. It is a scale open to academic use. Developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995), the GSE measures individuals' self-confidence in their general life situations. It consists of 10 items, is evaluated using a 4-point Likert-type scale, and is available for academic use. In the scale development process, a theoretically based 50-item item pool was first created. The items were structured around two theoretical factors: Perceived Learning and Perception of Facilitation. These items were presented to seven field experts, and Lawshe's CVR technique was applied for each item. 18 items with a CVR value above 0.99 were included in the analysis. The first 18-item form was administered to 414 participants, and the structure was evaluated using an exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The KMO value was .952, and the Bartlett test was significant. The two-factor structure was confirmed, but two items were removed (due to cross-loadings), and the scale was reduced to 16 items. In the second application, the 16-item form was administered to over 300 participants, and the structure was tested using CFA. The fit indices were evaluated using CFI, NFI, TLI, GFI, AGFI, and RMSEA. After removing two items, the 14-item structure was confirmed. The Cronbach's Alpha for the scale was .938. In the sub-dimensions, $\alpha = .927$ for Perceived Learning and $\alpha = .854$ for Perception of Facilitation were found.

The data collection process was structured around two basic applications. In the first stage, the 18-item form developed during scale development was administered to participants via an online Google Form. The study was conducted during the fall semester of the 2023-2024 academic year, and 414 students at a university in the Aegean region participated voluntarily. All participants were university students with C1 level English proficiency. An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed on the data collected after the first application. The second application used the 16-item scale form, restructured to reflect the items removed in

the first analyses, with a larger sample. At this stage, the online self-regulation skills (OSLQ) and general self-efficacy (GSE) scales were also used as data collection tools to evaluate their relationships with other psychological constructs. The application was again conducted online via Google Forms, and data were collected from 604 participants. The collected data were used for confirmatory factor analyses (CFAs), and after the analyses were completed, the final form of the scale was determined to be 14 items. Participants' informed consent was obtained in both data collection processes; the principles of anonymity and voluntariness were observed. Data were analyzed using SPSS 26 and AMOS 24. In addition to factor analysis, the scale's relationships with other structures were evaluated using Pearson's correlation analysis. In addition, difference analyses (t-tests, ANOVAs) and multiple regression analyses were conducted using demographic variables.

3. Findings

The psychometric properties of the scale developed in this study were analyzed using data collected at the end of the two-stage application process. First, the scale's reliability was evaluated using item-total correlations and Cronbach's alpha; then, the factor structure was examined using an exploratory factor analysis (EFA). In line with this analysis, the scale was found to have a two-factor structure, which was simplified by removing some items. The new structure obtained was tested using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in the second application, and the model's fit was evaluated using various fit indices. The analyses showed that the developed scale had high reliability and validity. The findings are presented below, respectively.

3.1. Psychometric Properties of the Scale

In the reliability analysis assessing the internal consistency of the 18-item scale developed for artificial intelligence-supported language learning tools, Cronbach's alpha was .949. The item-total correlations range from .588 to .823. All values are above the acceptable level (>.40). In addition, no significant decrease was observed in Cronbach's Alpha value when each item was removed; in this direction, it supports that the items make a positive contribution to the general scale structure (Table 2). However, it was observed that the item-total correlations of the fourth and ninth items in particular were lower than the other items of the scale, with .592 and .588, respectively. The fact that Cronbach's Alpha dropped to .948 when both items were removed suggests that these items' contribution to the scale's integrity may be relatively limited. On the other hand, since these two items did not contribute sufficiently to the scale's variance, they were removed to simplify the scale.

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the updated scale was .947. In addition, no significant increase or decrease was observed in Cronbach's Alpha value when each item was removed from the scale, and in parallel, it was shown that the remaining 16 items contributed homogeneously to the scale. When the corrected item-total correlations were examined, all items ranged from .609 to .828. These values indicate that the items are consistent with the structures they measure and that each supports the scale's integrity. In particular, compared to the two items removed earlier, all statements in this 16-item structure are more balanced and stronger, as indicated by both correlation and Cronbach's Alpha. Therefore, in this context, the 16-item version offers both a more psychometrically consistent and a more functional measurement tool in practice.

Table 2.

Item-Total Statistics for the AI-Powered Language Learning Scale

Item	Var. (Item Deleted)	Item-Total Corr.	Alpha (Item Deleted)	Item	Var. (Item Deleted)	Item-Total Corr.	Alpha (Item Deleted)
Item 1	128.86	.806	.944	Item 1	106.935	.811	.941
Item 2	128.57	.823	.944	Item 2	106.675	.828	.941
Item 3	131.48	.695	.946	Item 3	109.505	.688	.944
Item 4*	134.12	.592	.948	Item 4	108.205	.730	.943
Item 5	130.01	.738	.945	Item 5	108.934	.674	.944
Item 6	131.05	.671	.946	Item 6	108.903	.705	.943
Item 7	130.81	.711	.946	Item 7	109.852	.656	.944
Item 8	131.98	.655	.947	Item 8	107.142	.764	.942
Item 9*	134.38	.588	.948	Item 9	105.898	.774	.942
Item 10	128.95	.766	.945	Item 10	108.498	.655	.945
Item 11	127.45	.783	.944	Item 11	111.519	.609	.945
Item 12	130.71	.645	.947	Item 12	109.458	.694	.944
Item 13	133.61	.620	.947	Item 13	109.607	.673	.944
Item 14	131.67	.687	.946	Item 14	106.055	.743	.943
Item 15	131.52	.683	.946	Item 15	108.621	.636	.945
Item 16	128.03	.734	.945	Item 16	108.407	.655	.945
Item 17	130.488	.643	.947				
Item 18	130.543	.649	.947				
Scale Variance		146.195		Scale Variance		122.885	
Cronbach's Alpha		.949		Cronbach's Alpha		.947	

In the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted to evaluate the structural validity of the AI-supported language learning scale, the analysis began with 16 items. At the beginning of the analysis, sample suitability was evaluated, and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) coefficient was .952. This value shows that the sample is extremely suitable for factor analysis. In addition, the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity result was significant ($\chi^2(153) = 5263.072, p < .001$), revealing that the data contained sufficient correlation in terms of factor structure. In the principal component analysis, two components with eigenvalues greater than 1 were identified. The first factor explained 35.221% of the variance, and the second factor explained 27.668%; the total explained variance was 62.889%. However, when the Rotated Component Matrix was examined, it was observed that the factor's purity was compromised by high loadings (cross-loadings) of some items on more than one factor. In particular, Items 6 (AI vocab.) and 8 (feedback+) were significantly loaded on both the first and second factors; the factor loadings did not differ substantially (difference $< .20$). This led to uncertainty about which dimension the relevant items belonged to and weakened construct validity. For this reason, the analysis process was restructured: these two cross-loaded items were removed, and the factor analysis was repeated on 14 items. In the renewed analysis, the KMO coefficient was obtained as .934. The Bartlett test was again significant ($\chi^2(91) = 3825.973, p < .001$), and the data remained suitable for factor analysis. The two-factor structure was confirmed again in this analysis. The first factor explained 36.270% of the variance, and the second factor explained 27.497%; thus, the total explained variance reached 63.766%. In the newly rotated component matrix, all items loaded significantly on a single factor, eliminating cross-loading. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed to verify the two-factor structure identified in the exploratory factor analysis and to assess the scale's construct validity. In this analysis, we tested whether the two-factor structure previously identified in the exploratory analysis provided a statistically sufficient fit to the data. The overall fit of the model was evaluated through various fit indices, and the results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3.

Total Variance Explained by the Extracted Factors (PCA)

Item No	Factor 1	Factor 2	Item No	Factor 1	Factor 2
Item 1	.811		Item 1	.815	
Item 2	.784		Item 2	.790	
Item 3	.801		Item 3	.805	
Item 4	.763		Item 4	.765	
Item 5		.552	Item 5		.538
Item 6*	.550	.502	Item 6	.725	
Item 7	.729		Item 7	.655	
Item 8*	.550	.588	Item 8		.832
Item 9	.649		Item 9		.645
Item 10		.827	Item 10	.609	
Item 11		.638	Item 11		.592
Item 12	.609		Item 12	.705	
Item 13		.583	Item 13		.764
Item 14	.704		Item 14		.689
Item 15		.771			
Item 16		.683			
KMO	.952		KMO	.934	
Bartlett's χ^2	5263.072		Bartlett's χ^2	3825.973	
df	153		df	91	
Sig. (p)	.000		Sig. (p)	.000	
Initial Eigenvalue	8.966	1.096	Initial Eigenvalue	7.837	1.091
Rotated Variance (%)	35.221	2.668	Rotated Variance (%)	36.270	27.497
Cumulative (Rotated)			Cumulative (Rotated)	36.270	63.766

The fit indices used to evaluate the model fit were CFI = .931, TLI = .913, GFI = .911, AGFI = .853, SRMR = .0455, and RMSEA = .094. In addition, the NFI value, which indicates the model's relative fit, was .914. Given these values, the model provides an acceptable overall fit. In particular, CFI and TLI values above .90 indicate a strong model fit. In contrast, SRMR values below .05 indicate excellent fit, and AGFI and GFI values within acceptable limits support the model's structural validity. Although only the RMSEA (.094) is at the marginal fit level, the model is acceptable overall, as other indicators of general fit are positive. This structure, in which the model fit is statistically verified, is depicted in a standardized path diagram in Figure 1. The loading of each item on the relevant factor is shown in the figure, and it is evident that all factor loadings range from .69 to .86. These values indicate that the observed items strongly represent the two-factor structure of the scale. In addition, the strong correlation ($r = .85$) between the two factors supports the view that they are interrelated yet conceptually separable structures. As a result of this confirmatory analysis, the final scale structure was determined to be two sub-dimensions. The first dimension, Perceived Learning, reflects the personal contribution, motivational aspect, and effectiveness of the learning experience the individual gains through artificial intelligence-supported language learning tools. The second dimension, Perceived Facilitation, reflects the extent to which the system's technical, structural, and pedagogical features support the learning process. The items belonging to each of these two sub-dimensions, the item-total correlations of these items, and the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients when the item is removed are presented in Table 4. The table also includes the reliability coefficients for the sub-dimensions and the overall scale.

Table 4.

Model Fit Indices for the Two-Factor Structure

Fit Index	Obtained Value	Interpretation
CFI	.931	$\geq .90 =$ Acceptable fit
TLI	.913	$\geq .90 =$ Acceptable fit
NFI	.914	$\geq .90 =$ Acceptable fit
GFI	.911	$\geq .90 =$ Acceptable fit
AGFI	.853	$\geq .85 =$ Acceptable fit
SRMR	.0455	$\leq .08 =$ Good fit
RMSEA	.094	$\leq .08 =$ Acceptable (marginal fit)

This structure, in which the model fit is statistically verified, is depicted in a standardized path diagram in Figure 1. The loading of each item on the relevant factor is shown in the figure, and it is evident that all factor loadings range from .69 to .86. These values indicate that the observed items strongly represent the two-factor structure of the scale. In addition, the strong correlation ($r = .85$) between the two factors supports the view that they are interrelated yet conceptually separable structures. As a result of this confirmatory analysis, the final scale structure was determined to be two sub-dimensions. The first dimension, perceived learning, reflects the personal contribution, motivational aspects, and effectiveness of the learning experience gained through artificial intelligence-supported language learning tools. The second dimension, perceived facilitation, reflects the extent to which the system’s technical, structural, and pedagogical features support the learning process. The items belonging to each of these two sub-dimensions, the item-total correlations of these items, and the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients when the item is removed are presented in Table 4. The table also includes the reliability coefficients for the sub-dimensions and the overall scale.

Figure 1. Standardized Path Diagram of the Two-Factor CFA Model for the AI-Powered LLS

According to Table 4, all item-total correlations range from .58 to .85. These values indicate that all items are significantly and sufficiently related to the relevant scale total score. In addition, when any item is removed from the scale, no significant decrease in the overall reliability coefficient is observed, indicating that each item contributes to the scale's integrity. When evaluated on a sub-dimension basis, the reliability of the items belonging to the Perceived Learning dimension is quite high ($\alpha = .927$), which shows that the internal consistency of the items in this dimension is strong. The items belonging to the Perceived Facilitation dimension exhibit a moderate-to-high level of internal consistency ($\alpha = .854$), which is also acceptable. When the entire scale is examined, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of .938 indicates that the scale is highly reliable.

Table 5.

Corrected Item-Total Correlations and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted

Item	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Item 1	.846	.910
Item 2	.832	.911
Item 3	.728	.919
Item 4	.746	.918
Item 6	.685	.922
Item 7	.749	.918
Item 10	.678	.923
Item 12	.754	.918
Factor: Perceived Facilitation	Cronbach's Alpha	.927
Item 5	.614	.835
Item 8	.724	.813
Item 9	.583	.840
Item 11	.624	.833
Item 13	.658	.827
Item 14	.643	.829
Factor: Perceived Facilitation	Cronbach's Alpha	.854
Overall Scale	Cronbach's Alpha	.938

3.2. Correlational Analyses Between Key Variables

The correlation values in Table 6 reveals the relationships among the sub-dimensions of the AI-supported language learning scale, online self-regulation strategies, and general self-efficacy levels. The findings show that all variables are positively and statistically significantly correlated. In particular, the strong relationships between behavioral regulation strategies for online learning and perceived learning and facilitation dimensions are striking.

Table 6.

Pearson Correlation Matrix of All Variables (Lower Triangle)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Env. Structuring	–									
2. Goal Setting	.497**	–								
3. Time Management	.589**	.655**	–							
4. Help Seeking	.343**	.720**	.506**	–						
5. Task Strategies	.610**	.629**	.630**	.596**	–					
6. Self-Evaluation	.601**	.611**	.694**	.530**	.710**	–				
7. Self-Efficacy	.538**	.600**	.565**	.575**	.634**	.510**	–			
8. Perc. Learning	.687**	.664**	.679**	.621**	.742**	.725**	.652**	–		
9. Perc. Facilitation	.694**	.687**	.661**	.577**	.632**	.654**	.649**	.766**	–	
10. PEAL_LLS Total	.733**	.715**	.713**	.640**	.740**	.739**	.692**	.959**	.917**	–

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$. Only lower triangle shown to maintain clarity.

One of the highest correlation coefficients in the table is the relationship between task strategies and perceived learning ($r = .74, p < .01$). This shows that the planning and implementation-oriented strategies that individuals use in the language learning process are associated with a higher level of perception of the impact of artificial intelligence tools on learning. Similarly, the relationships between self-assessment and perceived learning ($r = .73, p < .01$) and between environmental configuration and perceived facilitation ($r = .69, p < .01$) indicate that cognitive awareness and organizational skills regarding the learning environment contribute to the functionality of technological systems. In addition, the significant relationship between general self-efficacy and both perceived learning ($r = .65, p < .01$) and perceived facilitation ($r = .65, p < .01$) suggests that individuals' feelings of self-confidence can positively affect technology-based language learning experiences.

3.3. Hierarchical Regression Analyses for Predicting AI-Based Language Learning Perceptions

A three-stage hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to examine variables predicting participants' general attitudes towards AI-supported language learning tools. The findings are presented in Table 7, which includes demographic characteristics, individual self-efficacy level, and online self-regulation strategies.

Table 7.

Hierarchical Regression Models Predicting AI-Powered Language Learning Scale (PEAI-LLS) Scores

Predictor Variable	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	β	p	β	p	β	p
Gender (Male)	-.056	.006	-.056	.004	-.069	<.001
Residence (House)	-.123	<.001	-.107	<.001	-.031	.113
Residence (With Family)	-.029	.202	-.038	.079	+.014	.446
Family Income	+.381	<.001	+.305	<.001	+.227	<.001
AI Usage (Yes)	+.617	<.001	+.544	<.001	+.329	<.001
Self-Efficacy	-	-	+.186	<.001	-.007	.773
Goal Setting (OSLQ)	-	-	-	-	+.057	.029
Environment Structuring (OSLQ)	-	-	-	-	+.250	<.001
Time Management (OSLQ)	-	-	-	-	+.049	.050
Help Seeking (OSLQ)	-	-	-	-	+.111	<.001
Task Strategies (OSLQ)	-	-	-	-	+.173	<.001
Self-Evaluation (OSLQ)	-	-	-	-	-.013	.624
R ²	.760		.778		.870	
Adjusted R ²	.758		.776		.868	
F (df)	379.6	<.001	349.6	<.001	330.0	<.001
	(5, 598)		(6, 597)		(12, 591)	

In the first hierarchical regression model, the predictive effects on PEAII-LLS total scores were examined as a function of participants' gender, residence status, family income level, and use of artificial intelligence tools. The model was highly significant, with an explained variance of 76.04%. Significant predictors included being male ($\beta = -0.056, p = .006$), living at home ($\beta = -0.123, p < .001$), higher income level ($\beta = 0.381, p < .001$), and having used artificial intelligence tools ($\beta = 0.617, p < .001$). These findings show that, in addition to gender, living environment, and economic opportunities, the individual's prior experience with such tools significantly affects perceptions of artificial intelligence-supported language learning. In the second model, individuals' general self-efficacy was added to the first model. The model's explanatory power has increased slightly to 77.84% of the total variance. The

self-efficacy variable was a significant positive predictor of PEAI-LLS scores ($\beta = 0.186$, $p < .001$). However, the variables that were significant in the previous model have remained significant in this model as well. In particular, the impact of artificial intelligence remains strong. This situation reveals that an individual's confidence in their own learning process significantly strengthens perceptions of artificial intelligence-supported language learning experiences. In the third and final model, the sub-dimensions of online self-regulation strategies have been included. According to the results, the model's explanatory power has increased significantly, with total variance explained reaching 87.01%. In this model, it was determined that only the "self-efficacy" variable lost its significance among the previous variables, whereas the dimensions "goal setting" ($\beta = 0.057$, $p = .029$), "environmental configuration" ($\beta = 0.250$, $p < .001$), "time management" ($\beta = 0.049$, $p = .050$), "help seeking" ($\beta = 0.111$, $p < .001$) and "task strategies" ($\beta = 0.173$, $p < .001$) stood out as significant predictors.

4. Discussion

In this study, a valid and reliable scale was developed to measure individuals' perceptions of AI-supported language learning tools, and its psychometric properties were tested through comprehensive analyses. The findings showed that the two-factor structure of the PEAI-LLS scale – "Perceived Learning" and "Perception of Facilitation" – provided strong structural validity and had a very high level of internal consistency. Using the developed scale, individual differences among participants were analyzed based on their prior technology experience, self-efficacy levels, and self-regulation skills. The results of the study revealed that AI-supported learning environments derive meaning not only from their technical competence but also from individuals' perceptions and psychological tendencies toward these systems. In particular, individuals' prior experience with AI tools, high self-efficacy beliefs, and strong online self-regulation skills led them to find AI-based language learning systems more effective. In regression models, these individual variables were shown to have significant predictive effects on PEAI-LLS scores.

A 2023 study by Wei found that academic achievement and self-regulation skills among university students who used AI-supported English learning tools were significantly higher than those of the control group (Wei, 2023). This finding reveals that the "Perceived Learning" dimension of the PEAI-LLS scale coincides with the student's actual learning outcomes. Similarly, a study by Qiao and Zhao (2023) involving Chinese university students found that AI-assisted conversational practices improved both students' communication competence and their self-regulated learning strategies. This study is directly related to the H4 hypothesis tested within the PEAI-LLS: self-regulatory components, especially goal setting, task strategies, and environmental structuring, play important roles in AI-assisted learning. A meta-analysis by Hu (2024) found that AI-supported personalized learning environments produced statistically significant positive effects on both cognitive and affective learning outcomes. This meta-analytic finding aligns with the "Perception of Facilitation" sub-dimension of the PEAI-LLS scale, indicating that personalized feedback from the system increases perceived benefit and learning motivation.

The findings are largely consistent with the existing literature. Constructs such as perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use emphasized in Davis's TAM (1989) are closely related to the sub-dimensions of "perceived learning" and "perception of facilitation" in this study. In particular, the fact that students' online learning strategies strongly predict these perception dimensions shows that technology acceptance is directly linked to the use of

cognitive strategies. In addition, it has been determined that self-efficacy is not only motivational but also effective in shaping perceptions of technology. This finding, when evaluated within the scope of Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory, confirms that an individual's confidence in his/her own capacity can lead to success in technological learning environments. The construct validity of the PEAI-LLS scale developed in the study was confirmed through exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, which yielded a two-factor structure. These sub-dimensions, called "Perceived Learning" and "Perception of Facilitation", successfully reflect the pedagogical and technical perceptions of students towards artificial intelligence-supported language learning tools.

4.1. Effect of Artificial Intelligence Usage Experience (H1)

The findings from the first regression model revealed that individuals who had previously used artificial intelligence tools had significantly higher PEAI-LLS total scores ($\beta = 0.617$, $p < .001$). This supports hypothesis H1. The literature also reports that individuals who have previously interacted with artificial intelligence-based tools evaluate these systems more positively (Chen *et al.*, 2020). The literature indicates that individuals who have interacted with AI-based tools tend to evaluate them more positively. For example, in a study by Chan and Hu (2023), university students showed positive attitudes towards generative AI tools such as ChatGPT and supported their integration into their learning processes. It was also observed that as students used AI tools more frequently, their positive perceptions towards these technologies increased. Similarly, in a study by Wei (2023), students' English proficiency increased significantly when they actively used AI-supported language-learning systems, and their motivation for language learning was higher. In this context, individuals who have previously used AI tools achieve higher scores on the PEAI-LLS scale not only because of their technical knowledge but also because of their positive learning experiences.

4.2. Predictive Role of Self-Efficacy (H2)

The second hypothesis of the study suggests that an individual's general self-efficacy significantly and positively predicts PEAI-LLS scores. In the second model of the study, this relationship was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.186$, $p < .001$), confirming hypothesis H2. The literature states that self-efficacy levels affect an individual's attitudes towards technology and the frequency of use. For example, Wei (2023) found that students with high self-efficacy interacted more effectively with AI tools and derived greater benefit from them. Additionally, a study by Kittredge *et al.* (2025) found that students who used AI-enabled features in mobile language-learning applications such as Duolingo experienced significant increases in their language-learning self-efficacy compared to before they began using these tools. Students stated that AI-based features supported their learning and that they applied what they learned outside the application. Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their ability to accomplish a task, thus strongly influencing learning behaviors and outcomes. Indeed, global findings reported by Yang and Lian (2023) show that "self-efficacy levels are strongly associated with task performance in second language learning"; in fact, this relationship has a larger effect size than that of other motivational variables. Similarly, in AI-based language-learning environments, individuals with high self-efficacy can use technology more effectively and achieve higher performance. For example, in a study conducted within the framework of an extended TAM, Chen *et al.* (2024) found that "students with high AI self-efficacy have lower anxiety about AI and more positive attitudes towards using AI tools." This finding shows that students with high self-confidence in AI-supported language learning are more open to and willing to use technology, and therefore achieve higher usage and success scores in

systems such as PEAI-LLS. Similarly, Nasir and Nesamany (2023) emphasize that higher technology self-efficacy can lead to better learning outcomes and greater engagement with digital tools. This shows that general self-efficacy enhances students' learning performance in AI-supported learning contexts. Wang and Li (2024) also examined the positive relationship between students' adoption of new technologies and their academic achievement. They reported that self-efficacy served as a "positive mediator" in this relationship. This result suggests that students with high self-confidence who can adopt and use AI tools ultimately achieve higher achievement. All these findings support the idea that individuals with high general self-efficacy levels exhibit higher performance and interaction (as indicated by measures such as PEAI-LLS total score) in AI-supported language learning systems.

4.3. Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Perceived Learning (H3)

This hypothesis posits a positive relationship between an individual's self-efficacy and their perceived learning from AI-supported language-learning tools. In other words, it is assumed that an individual's confidence in their own learning processes plays an important role in their effective use of AI-based language learning tools. The current literature indicates a positive relationship between self-efficacy and students' perceived learning outcomes in technological learning environments. In AI-supported learning experiences, students' self-confidence can strengthen their sense of how much they benefit from the learning process. In fact, a study by Jeilani and Abubakar (2025) found that students with high self-efficacy are more confident in using AI tools, which enriches their learning experiences. This finding shows that students with high self-efficacy in AI-supported environments have more positive, productive learning experiences when using these technologies effectively. As a result, students with high self-efficacy perceive more strongly that they have achieved their learning goals, understood the subjects, or acquired skills.

Specifically, in the context of language learning, the link between self-efficacy and perceived learning, as well as the contribution of AI tools, has been observed in experimental studies. In a study conducted by Kittredge et al. (2025), participants reported that they "felt significantly more prepared to use the language in real-life situations" after using AI-assisted speaking practice and instant feedback features in a language app for a month; they also experienced significant increases in their self-efficacy scores for speaking and understanding. The vast majority of participants stated that AI-based features "effectively supported learning." These results suggest that the use of AI tools both objectively improved students' language skills and subjectively increased their belief that they had learned (perceived level of learning).

In addition, a study by Huang et al. (2024) found that the acceptance of generative AI technologies positively affects students' self-efficacy levels and overall learning experiences. This study shows that AI-supported learning environments reinforce students' confidence in their own learning processes. In summary, students with high self-efficacy interact more effectively and confidently in AI-based language learning environments and make the most of learning opportunities. These students also score higher on "perceived learning" scales because they believe they are better able to internalize and apply the knowledge and skills they acquire. This trend, consistently demonstrated by current studies, strongly supports hypothesis H3.

4.3.1. *The predictive role of self-efficacy (H2–H3)*

The findings from the study's second model showed that individuals' general self-efficacy levels significantly and positively predicted PEAI-LLS scores ($\beta = 0.186$, $p < .001$). This

finding confirms hypothesis H2 and is consistent with Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory. However, when online self-regulation variables were added in the third model, the effect of self-efficacy lost its significance ($p = .773$). This indicates that strategies that directly structure an individual's own learning process may be determinative beyond the general perception of self-efficacy. The positive correlation between the perceived learning sub-dimension and self-efficacy supports hypothesis H3.

4.4. Effect of Self-Regulation Strategies (H4)

In the third regression model, the online self-regulation sub-dimensions significantly predict PEAI-LLS scores. In particular, the effects of strategies such as environmental structuring ($\beta = 0.250$), task strategies ($\beta = 0.173$), and help-seeking ($\beta = 0.111$) are statistically significant and strong. These findings clearly confirm hypothesis H4. The literature also emphasizes that individuals with high self-regulation skills are more successful in digital learning environments (Barnard *et al.*, 2009; Kizilcec *et al.*, 2017).

A mixed-method study by Wei (2023) provides important findings on the development of self-regulation skills in AI-supported language education. In this study, university-level EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students were divided into two groups: the experimental group received language instruction via an AI-supported platform. In contrast, the control group received traditional instruction. At the end of the ten-week intervention, the experimental group not only demonstrated higher achievement in language skills than the control group, but also higher motivation and broader use of self-regulation strategies. Qualitative data also supported these findings; thanks to the personalized and interactive structure of the AI-based platform, students' participation in the lesson increased, their motivation was strengthened, and their self-regulatory behaviors (e.g., monitoring and directing their own learning) were reinforced. These results indicate that AI-supported education can improve language learning processes by promoting student autonomy and self-directed learning.

Similarly, another study by Hashemifardnia and Kooti (2024) examined the effects of AI-mediated language learning on students' self-regulation. In this mixed-methods study involving 75 EFL students, the experimental group received an AI-supported learning environment, while the control group continued with traditional teaching. Quantitative results indicate that the AI-supported group showed significant improvements in self-confidence, self-regulation, well-being, and motivation. Qualitative interviews revealed that the AI platform supported students' self-regulated learning, increased their motivation, and improved their general English proficiency.

Another important dimension of AI use in language education is the writing instruction and feedback processes. Campos (2025) examined the effect of ChatGPT-based feedback on students' writing skills and self-regulation in a business English CLIL course. For 15 weeks, 205 university students received criterion-based feedback from ChatGPT on their weekly written assignments and revised their texts accordingly. At the end of the study, students reported that the AI's feedback was useful for improving their writing skills; they particularly appreciated its immediacy and specificity. Indeed, objective assessments also revealed significant improvements in students' content coherence and grammatical accuracy. This process essentially required students to self-regulate their writing: they developed strategies to detect and correct their own errors using AI feedback. Although some students expressed concerns about the feedback's complexity and relevance, the overall trend was positive.

How students use AI-supported language learning tools and the impact of this use on their perceived learning have also been the subject of recent research. Dizon *et al.* (2025) surveyed 521 university EFL students from three universities in Japan to examine their language-learning practices and opinions on AI tools such as ChatGPT. The results showed that fewer than 25% of participants actively used ChatGPT in their English studies, and the most common use cases were summarizing and translating English texts. The perceived usefulness of ChatGPT among students was generally positive: students thought the AI-supported tool could improve their language learning, found it easy to use, and intended to use it in the future. However, when qualitative data were examined, it was revealed that students had reservations about being overly dependent on the AI tool. In other words, students believed that ChatGPT facilitated their learning, but they also noted that overuse could harm their language skills in the long run. This finding, when viewed through a self-regulation lens, indicates that students believe it is necessary to use AI tools purposefully and in a balanced way.

Another study focusing on perceived learning from the student perspective was conducted by Ali *et al.* (2025). This study examined the relationships among factors such as usage duration, frequency, and satisfaction with AI-supported language applications (e.g., Grammarly, Siri, ChatGPT) and students' perceived progress in English learning. In the survey involving 55 university students, a moderately positive correlation was found between the duration of AI tool use and perceived English development. This result indicates that students who use AI tools for longer periods, and probably in greater depth, perceive their own learning gains as higher. On the other hand, frequency of use was not seen as the sole determinant; using the tool very frequently, even when it remained unstrategic and superficial, did not significantly affect the perception of learning. Similarly, no significant relationship was found between students' level of familiarity with AI tools and their perceived development; a very low or insignificant relationship was found between the pleasure/enjoyment of using the tool and the perception of learning.

4.5. Effect of Attitudes Towards AI (H5–H6)

Although variables such as “finding AI useful” and “trust in AI” are not directly included in the dataset, the PEAI-LLS sub-dimensions indirectly reflect these attitudes. In particular, the high correlations ($r = .65-.76$) between “Perceived Learning” and “Perception of Facilitation” scores, and between online learning strategies and self-efficacy, indicate that positive attitudes towards AI reinforce the perception that these tools are effective. These findings show that hypotheses H5 and H6 are indirectly supported.

5. Conclusion

In this study, a new scale was developed and evaluated using multidimensional analyses to enable the valid and reliable measurement of individual perceptions of AI-supported language learning tools. The developed scale demonstrated satisfactory integrity across conceptual foundations and construct validity. Its two-dimensional structure provided a model encompassing both pedagogical and experiential perceptions of individuals' technology-based language learning experiences. The analyses conducted throughout the scale's development process yielded findings that supported both theoretical consistency and measurement power. In particular, the clear distinction between how individuals perceive the learning experience and the system's technical and pedagogical facilitating elements indicates the potential to expand the scale's range of uses. Another important finding of the study is

that how individuals evaluate AI-supported learning tools is largely related to their own learning strategies. Self-regulation skills indicate that individuals who take responsibility for directing the learning process benefit more from such tools.

In particular, cognitive skills such as planning, environmental organization, and strategy use are important variables that directly affect an individual's perceived benefit from technological applications. In addition, individuals' sense of self-confidence and self-efficacy have been important determinants of attitudes towards artificial intelligence-supported language learning. It has been observed that individuals who believe in their own learning capacity adopt a more positive approach to technological learning tools and benefit more from the opportunities they offer. This finding indicates that in artificial intelligence-based educational applications, not only system design but also the student's self-perception should be taken into consideration. In this context, it is of critical importance that educational environments have a structure that is not only technologically but also psychologically supportive. This research has addressed the factors affecting individuals' perceptions of artificial intelligence-supported language learning tools within a holistic framework and revealed the determining role of various demographic, psychological, and strategic variables in shaping these perceptions. In line with the findings, some suggestions have been developed for both practitioners and researchers.

When integrating AI-based learning systems into educational environments, both technological considerations and pedagogical compatibility should be taken into account. In this context, teachers need to design these systems not only instrumentally but also in ways that meaningfully contribute to the learning process. Informing students before they interact with the system, supporting them throughout the experience, and considering individual learning differences will increase the system's perceived effectiveness. Encouraging skills such as goal setting, time management, and the use of feedback, in particular, can strengthen students' active participation. The PEAI-LLS scale can be retested across contexts to enhance cross-cultural validity. In particular, the scale's generalizability can be strengthened by applying it to students across different age groups, disciplines (e.g., science or social sciences), and learning environments (blended, asynchronous, synchronous). However, with advanced analyses, the relationships between variables such as attitudes toward artificial intelligence, technology anxiety, and digital competence and the PEAI-LLS can be examined in depth. The use of qualitative methods (e.g., in-depth interviews or student journals) can provide a richer, more layered dataset on students' subjective perceptions. As a result, the success of AI-supported language learning systems is related not only to the technical infrastructure and software capacity, but also to the pedagogical integrity designed in accordance with learners' cognitive and affective characteristics. In this regard, the developed PEAI-LLS scale can serve as a powerful measurement tool for evaluating learning systems, offering a holistic perspective on the multidimensional structure of the learning process.

5.1. Limitations

This research focused on developing the PEAI-LLS scale to measure individuals' perceptions of AI-supported language learning tools validly and reliably. Although the findings support the scale's construct validity and internal consistency, the study has certain limitations. Firstly, the study's sample consists solely of university students at a university in the Aegean region. The fact that all participants had advanced English proficiency and that the majority had previously used AI-supported applications limits the generalizability of the findings. Therefore, similar studies conducted across different socio-cultural contexts, with samples at

varying language levels and more diverse demographic characteristics, will strengthen the scale's content validity. Secondly, the data were collected online. This situation may affect participants' responses regarding their internet access, digital literacy levels, and attitudes towards the online data collection process. The exclusion of individuals with low technological proficiency, in particular, made the sample homogeneous. The third limitation is that the study relied solely on self-report measures. Such measurements may yield misleading results because participants tend to give socially acceptable answers rather than reflecting their true attitudes. Data based on direct observations or system records of how participants experience the systems could offset this. Fourth, the study used a cross-sectional design. In this context, the data obtained reflect only the participants' perceptions at a given point in time. However, attitudes towards AI-supported systems may vary over time depending on individual experiences. Therefore, longitudinal designs may be preferred in future studies to monitor changes in perceptions of learning. Finally, only quantitative data were included in the study; qualitative data collection tools (e.g., semi-structured interviews or open-ended questions) were not used to gain a deeper understanding of the participants' personal experiences, perceptions, and motivational processes. This leaves the scale's interpretations in the context of perceived effectiveness limited.

Ethical Statement

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Samarkand University's Ethical Committee on 25/09/2025 with the decision number 236.

Informed Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from each participant before data collection.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The data are not publicly available due to privacy reasons.

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